

Semi-rapid procedures for the analysis of microcrustacean zooplankton samples

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PURPOSE AND SCOPE

These procedures are designed to standardize the routine analysis of zooplankton samples, focusing on microcrustaceans. The aim is to generate key metrics, such as the abundance and biovolume of the main taxonomic groups, which are commonly used in baseline monitoring programs. By optimizing the cost-effectiveness and efficiency of sample processing, the protocols aim to promote the widespread use of zooplankton as an indicator of biological water quality. The entire process, excluding the settling time required for the biovolume settling method (described below), should take approximately half a day. The materials required are commonly available in biological laboratories or can be easily procured.

Three distinct procedures are outlined to quantify:

1. The whole-sample zooplankton biovolume
2. The abundance of individual counting units
3. The biomass of individual counting units

BEFORE YOU START

1. Field data sheet

Ensure the zooplankton sample is accompanied by a completed field data sheet. The sheet should include, at a minimum:

- Date of collection
- Sampling location
- Sampling depth (or depth range, e.g. 0-50 m)
- Volume of lakewater filtered

2. Counting Units (CUs)

Clearly define the Counting Units (CUs) for your analysis. To optimize for time efficiency, select CUs that can be reliably identified using a dissecting microscope at low to moderate magnification (20–40x). The resolution will depend on taxon and life stage:

- **Cladocerans and Adult Copepods:** These can typically be identified to species or species complexes and may be separated further by sex.

- **Immature Copepods (Copepodids):** In samples with only a few clearly different species (e.g., 2–3 species of varying sizes), identification to species is possible. Otherwise, identification to genus or family is preferred.
- **Nauplii:** These are not identified further or classified as either calanoids or cyclopoids. For detailed CU examples, refer to Appendix 1.

3. Define the special categories of Large and Rare Zooplankton (LRZ) and Small Zooplankton (SZ)

- **Large and Rare Zooplankton (LRZ):** This category includes large, predatory cladocerans (e.g., *Leptodora*, *Bythotrephes*) and other rare taxa that could be missed if only small subsamples are analyzed.
- **Small Zooplankton (SZ):** Typically includes nauplii, but may also encompass other small, abundant zooplankton such as small copepodids. These categories should be counted separately.

4. Learn to identify any unfamiliar CUs

If you are not familiar with any CUs that you are likely to encounter in the sample (check previous lists, if available), learn to identify them. Identification of microcrustaceans typically requires detailed examination under a compound microscope, which should be avoided during routine counting to maintain efficiency.

5. Laboratory Data Sheet

Prepare a laboratory data sheet to record the tally of each CU and associated information (e.g., taxonomic group, abundance, biovolume, etc.). A sample data sheet is provided in Appendix 1 for reference.

6. Replace any toxic fixative with non-toxic alternatives

If the sample was stored using a toxic fixative (e.g., formaldehyde), follow these steps:

- Filter the sample using a fine mesh sieve.
- Rinse the sample thoroughly with tap water.
- Transfer the sample to a 70–80% ethanol solution.

Follow standard safety protocols when handling hazardous chemicals (e.g., wear gloves, work in a fume hood, etc.).

MATERIALS

- Separating funnel (1 L)
- Sieve, with a mesh size slightly finer than the mesh of the sampling net (e.g., choose a 90 μm sieve if a 100 μm net was used for sampling)
- Graduated tube (e.g., 30 mL)
- Squeeze bottle
- A wide-bore pipette for aspirating small and large zooplankton. An 'Eppendorf®'-type 10 mL pipette with the tip cut back by ca. 1 cm (so that the hole diameter is 4 mm) is ideal. This pipette allows quick adjustment of the sampling volume of the sub-samples (cf. below).
- Dissecting microscope with 10-40x magnification
- Calibrated micrometer inserted in one of the microscope eyepieces

- Petri dishes: A 9-10 cm dish and a 3-6 cm dish. Guiding lines engraved every ~2 mm on the bottom help avoid double-counting while scanning.
 - Bogorov counting chamber (or another suitable chamber)
 - Mixing bottle: Indicatively, from 100 to 500 mL, depending on sample volume
 - Laboratory sheet
 - Dishwashing detergent
 - Fine-mounted needle
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STEP-BY-STEP PROCEDURES

1. Whole-Sample Biovolume (Settling Volume Method)

1. Pour the entire zooplankton sample into the separating funnel.
2. Let the zooplankton settle until most of it is settled at the bottom of the funnel (up to 2 hours).
3. Collect the settled zooplankton in the graduated tube by opening the funnel's tap.
4. Let the zooplankton settle in the graduated tube (up to 1-2 hours).
5. Pour the supernatant from the graduated tube (which may still contain small zooplankton) back into the separating funnel.
6. Stir the contents of the separating funnel.
7. Let the zooplankton remaining in the separating funnel settle for a few more hours.
8. Repeat steps 3–6 until all zooplankton have been collected into the graduated tube. For the last repetition, let the remaining zooplankton settle for 12 hours (or overnight).
9. Once all zooplankton have been transferred to the graduated tube, wait 2 hours for all zooplankton to settle. Note the biovolume of the settled zooplankton in the graduated tube (this is the 'settled zooplankton biovolume', SBV, in mL). Ignore any phytoplankton settling above the zooplankton.
10. Filter the remaining contents of the separating funnel using the sieve.
11. Transfer the filtered fraction and the contents of the graduated tube to the original jar or mixing bottle to reconstitute the original sample. Add 80% alcohol as needed for preservation.

General Notes

- Transfer the zooplankton into the graduated tube over multiple repeats (see pt. 8) rather than all at once. If too much zooplankton settles at the bottom of the funnel, the funnel's tap may clog.
- Choose a smaller graduated tube (e.g. 10 or 20 mL) with graduations every 0.5 mL if the overall volume is small.

2. Counting Unit (CU) Abundance (Microscopic Counts)

1. Sample preparation

1. Dilute or reduce the original sample to a known volume (e.g., 300-500 mL). As a general guideline, a volume of 400-500 mL may work for samples collected with one net haul in a mesotrophic or eutrophic lake.

- If the sample is too dilute (i.e., the subsample volume needed to count 50-100 individuals is too large, >5 mL), concentrate it.
 - If the sample is too concentrated (i.e., the subsample volume needed to count 50-100 individuals is too small, <1 mL), dilute it.
2. Note the total volume of the sample in the laboratory sheet.

2. Sample handling

3. Place the whole sample into a mixing bottle.
4. Add a drop of dishwashing detergent. Mix the sample using a cross-pattern motion or by inverting the bottle several times. Avoid creating vortices with circular movements.

3. Estimating the optimal subsample volume

5. Using the pipette, take a small subsample (e.g., 1-5 mL) and place it in a Petri dish.
6. Scan the Petri dish under the dissecting microscope to estimate the total number of microcrustaceans (excluding SZ).
 - Estimate the subsample volume needed to collect 50-100 individuals per subsample, including LRT but excluding SZ.
 - Adjust the subsample volume if needed based on the count.
7. Note the chosen subsample volume on the laboratory sheet.

4. Counting

8. After adjusting the pipette's volume, take a new subsample and place it in the counting chamber.
9. Allow the zooplankton to settle in the counting chamber.
10. Using the dissecting microscope, identify and count all microcrustacean CUs (excluding SZ) in the counting chamber.
11. If a Bogorov chamber is used:
 - Begin counting from one end of the chamber's sinuous groove, moving slowly towards the other end.
 - Use a magnification that allows viewing the entire width of the groove (e.g., ~20x), switching to a higher magnification when necessary for identification.
12. Record the tally of all CUs counted on the laboratory sheet.
13. Repeat steps 8-11 until a total of 300-400 microcrustaceans (excluding SZ) are counted. Ensure that at least 3 subsamples are examined.

5. Adjustments for Efficiency

14. If the microcrustaceans in the first subsample are too abundant (>100 individuals) or hard to count (e.g., during phytoplankton blooms), discard the subsample, reduce the volume, and repeat the process.
15. If a CU is too abundant in the first subsample (>50 individuals), count the other CUs first, then take smaller subsamples and count all CUs.

6. Stop counting earlier for dominant CUs

16. Once more than 50 individuals of a CU have been counted across subsamples, stop counting that CU in subsequent subsamples. This reduces inaccuracy in the count of nondominant CUs, especially in cases where one CU is highly dominant (e.g., during

Daphnia peaks). The calculation equations (see CALCULATIONS) account for the smaller proportion of the sample analyzed.

7. Additional counts for Large and Rare Taxa (LRT)

17. Take a large subsample (10% of the total sample volume).
18. Place the subsample in a larger Petri dish.
19. Systematically scan the dish and count all LRT under low magnification (10x or closest available).
20. Count up to 50 LRT individuals. If there are more than 50 LRT individuals, discard the subsample and repeat with a smaller volume (e.g., 5% of the total sample).
21. If there are fewer than 5 LRT individuals, take a second subsample and repeat.
22. Report counts and subsample volume on the laboratory sheet.

8. Counting Smaller Zooplankton (SZ)

23. Take a small subsample (1% or less of the total sample volume).
24. Place it in a smaller Petri dish.
25. Count all SZ under high magnification (40x or the closest available).
26. Aim to count at least 100 SZ individuals. If the dish contains more than 100 SZ, discard the subsample and repeat with a smaller volume (e.g., 0.5%).
27. Report the tally and subsample volume on the laboratory sheet.

General Notes

- Counting SZ separately in a Petri dish is often more efficient than counting directly in the counting chamber, as SZ is often more abundant and requires different subsample volumes.
- It is recommended to count 3-4 subsamples to reduce subsampling errors in the estimate of whole-sample abundances. Multiple smaller subsamples tend to provide better accuracy than one or two larger ones.

3. Counting-Unit (CU) Biomass (Microscopic Measurements)

1. Measure the body length of the first 20 individuals of each CU encountered while counting (or all individuals if fewer than 20) using an eyepiece micrometer. Use a fixed magnification of 20x (or the nearest available magnification).
2. Report the individual lengths in the laboratory sheet for each CU.

CALCULATIONS

The following calculations assume that the sample was collected using a plankton net.

1. Total zooplankton biovolume (BV) per m³ of lake-water filtered:

$$BV \text{ (mL m}^{-3}\text{)} = SBV \text{ (mL)} \div \text{Volume filtered}$$

Where:

SBV = Settled zooplankton biovolume (mL), from procedure 1.

Volume filtered (m³) = Volume filtered by the net; ≈ tow length (m) x net mouth area (m²)

2. Total zooplankton biovolume (BV) per m² of lake surface:

$$BV \text{ (mL m}^{-2}\text{)} = SBV \text{ (mL)} \div \text{Net area (m}^2\text{)}$$

Where:

SBV = Settled zooplankton biovolume (mL), from procedure 1.

Net area = net mouth area (m²)

3. CU abundance per m³ of lake-water filtered:

$$\text{Abundance (ind m}^{-3}\text{)} = \frac{N \text{ (ind)}}{p \times \text{Volume filtered (m}^3\text{)}}$$

Where:

N = Number of organisms counted across all subsamples analyzed (ind)

p = proportion of sample volume analyzed (unitless), i.e.:

$$p = (\text{subsampling volume} \times \text{no. subsamples}) / \text{total sample volume}$$

Volume filtered = see pt. 1

4. CU abundance per m² of lake surface:

$$\text{Abundance (ind m}^{-2}\text{)} = \frac{N \text{ (ind)}}{p \times \text{Net area (m}^2\text{)}}$$

Where:

N and p = see pt. 3

Net area = see pt. 2

5. Average CU individual weight

Estimate individual weight (μg dry weight, DW) of each individual measured within each CU (up to 20) using an appropriate length-mass regression. Sources of published regression models are provided in the LITERATURE section. Calculate the average to obtain the average individual CU weight (AIW, in μg).

6. CU biomass per m³ of lake-water filtered:

$$\text{Biomass (mg DW m}^{-3}\text{)} = \frac{N \text{ (ind)} \times \text{AIW (}\mu\text{g)} \times 1000}{p \times \text{Volume filtered (m}^3\text{)}}$$

Where:

N and p = see pt. 3

Volume filtered = see pt. 1

AIW = average individual CU weight (in μg). See pt. 5.

7. CU biomass per m^2 of lake surface:

$$\text{Biomass (mg m}^{-2}\text{)} = \frac{N \text{ (ind)} \times \text{AIW (}\mu\text{g)} \times 1000}{p \times \text{Net area (m}^2\text{)}}$$

Where:

N and p: see pt. 3

Net area = see pt. 2

AIW = average individual weight (in μg). See pt. 5.

QUALITY CONTROL AND ASSURANCE

1. Comparison with historical data

Compare the results of the current sample with those from previous and subsequent samples collected from the same station. Ideally, these samples should be collected within one month.

2. Sampling conditions:

Document environmental conditions during sampling (e.g., storms, equipment clogging due to phytoplankton or debris). Exclude (or flag) samples collected under sub-optimal conditions to ensure consistent data quality.

3. Subsampling:

Ensure that the abundance and composition across subsamples are consistent. If a subsample is noticeably different, discard it and collect a new one to maintain homogeneity.

SAFETY WARNINGS

- The primary safety hazards are related to the fixatives used in the process.
- If a toxic fixative (e.g., formaldehyde) is used, transfer the sample to a non-toxic fixative as soon as possible to minimize risk (see BEFORE YOU START, pt. 6).

TIME REQUIRED

- **Biovolume Calculation:** Approximately 1 hour per zooplankton sample (excluding settling time).
- **Abundance and Biomass Determination:** Approximately 3-4 hours.

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LITERATURE

- Bledzki, L.A. and Rybak, J.I. (2016) Freshwater Crustacean Zooplankton of Europe: Cladocera & Copepoda (Calanoida, Cyclopoida). Key to species identification, with notes on ecology, distribution, methods and introduction to data analysis. Springer.
- Bottrell, H.H., Duncan, A., Gliwicz, Z.M., Grygierek, E., Herzig, A., Hillbricht-Ilkowska, A., Kurosawa, H., Larsson, P. and Weglenska, T. (1976) A review of some problems in zooplankton production studies. *Norw. J. Zool.*, 24: 419-456.
- Bowen, K.L. (2017) Methods for the determination of zooplankton density, biomass and secondary production. Canadian Manuscript Report of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences 3119. Fisheries and Oceans Canada. https://publications.gc.ca/collections/collection_2018/mpo-dfo/Fs97-4-3119-eng.pdf
- Dumont, H.J., van de Velde, I. and Dumont, S. (1975) The dry weight estimate of biomass in a selection of Cladocera, Copepoda and Rotifera from the plankton, periphyton and benthos of continental waters. *Oecologia*, 19: 75-97.
- Edmonson, W.T. and Winberg, G.T. (1971) A manual on methods for the assessment of secondary production in fresh waters. IBP Handbook No. 17.
- McCallum, I. D. (1979) A simple method of taking a subsample of zooplankton. *N. Z. J. Mar. Freshw. Res.*, 13: 559-560.
- U.S. Environmental Protection Agency EPA (2016). Standard Operating Procedure for Zooplankton Analysis. LG403, Revision 07, July 2016. <https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2017-01/documents/sop-for-zooplankton-analysis-201607-22pp.pdf>
- Watkins, J., Rudstam, L. and Holeck, K. (2011) Length-weight regressions for zooplankton biomass calculations—A review and a suggestion for standard equations. <https://ecommons.cornell.edu/items/5f491e81-2f43-4347-b944-ae116b41834f>